

The PDI model system in Python – a short tutorial

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The PDI (“Peters-Durner-Iden”) model system parameterizes soil hydraulic properties over the full moisture range and accounts for water retention and conductivity in partially-filled pores (adsorption and film-flow). The model was developed in stages and the respective literature is cited at the end of this document. A comprehensive overview of the model development and the model equations is provided in Peters et al. (2024). The Python scripts in this repository and their documentation are directly linked to this research article. Neither the theory nor the equations are repeated in this short tutorial, users are referred to Peters et al., (2024) for this information.

We provide a Python file named `"pdi.py"` that can be used to compute the various functions of the PDI model family. Table 1 gives an overview of supported models alongside their corresponding Python functions (listed in the 3rd column). For most users, the PDI model with the saturation function based on van Genuchten (1980) will be the primary option. This tutorial is therefore focused on explaining the usage of the `"pdi_vg"` function. The use of the other functions implementing the PDI model system, namely `pdi_vg_mn`, `pdi_kos`, `pdi_fx`, `pdi_vg_bi`, `pdi_kos_bi`, should be straightforward; only the parameter vector (np.array) `'p'` differs among them. Table 1 outlines the order of model parameters within the `'p'` array.

We provide some example scripts illustrating the use of the PDI functions. Table 2 lists these scripts along with their respective functionalities. The function `'export_hydrus_materin'` writes a table of the soil hydraulic properties to an ASCII file “MATER.IN” that can be used for simulations with Hydrus-1D and Hydrus-2D3D.

pdi_vg (p, h, TC, lcap, lcon, optkc, optknc, lvap, ldiff)

Parameters:

p: array-like with shape (n,)

Array containing the model parameters, see Table 1 for correct order

h: array like with shape (n,)

Array containing the soil water suction in [cm]

TC: float

Temperature in [°C], used to calculate the temperature dependent components of hydraulic conductivity. Default is 20°C

lcap: logical / Boolean

Controls whether the soil water capacity is computed, default is `False`.

If `ldiff == True`, the capacity will be calculated but not returned to the calling function.

lcon: logical / Boolean

Controls whether the soil hydraulic conductivity is computed, default is `True`.

optkc: { 'taus', 'ksc' }

How to calculate the capillary hydraulic conductivity function, default is 'taus'.

'taus': Prediction of the absolute capillary hydraulic conductivity $K_c(h)$, see Eq. (16) in Peters et al. (2024). In case of the PDI-VG model, $\text{taus} = 0.062$.

'ksc': Scaling of a relative capillary conductivity function by the saturated capillary conductivity, $K_c(h) = K_{sc}K_{rc}(h)$, see Eq. (12) and (13) in Peters et al. (2024)

optknc: { 'pred', 'cfilm', 'ksnc' }

How to calculate the noncapillary hydraulic conductivity function, default is 'predict'

'pred': Prediction of the absolute hydraulic conductivity, see Eq. (21) in Peters et al. (2024). The value of parameter c is calculated internally, the position in array p can be left empty.

'cfilm': Prediction of the absolute hydraulic conductivity, see Eq. (21) in Peters et al., (2024). The value of parameter c must be passed to the function as part of parameter vector p .

'ksnc': Scaling of a relative noncapillary conductivity function by the saturated noncapillary conductivity, $K_{nc}(h) = K_{snc}K_{rnc}(h) = K_{snc} \left(\frac{h_0}{h_a}\right)^{-1.5(1-S_4)}$, the parameter K_{snc} must be passed to the function.

lvap: logical / Boolean

Controls whether the isothermal vapor conductivity is computed, default

is `False`

`ldiff`: logical / Boolean

Controls whether the soil water diffusivity function is computed, default is `False`.

Returns:

`pdi`: SimpleNamespace containing the following entries:

- `thc`: ndarray, shape (n,)
volumetric water content [-] due to capillary storage
- `thnc`: ndarray, shape (n,)
volumetric water content [-] due to noncapillary storage (sorption)
- `th`: ndarray, shape (n,)
volumetric water content [-] for the user-specified suctions h
- `cap`: ndarray, shape (n,)
soil water capacity [cm^{-1}] if `lcap == True`
- `kc`: ndarray, shape (n,)
capillary hydraulic conductivity $K_c(h)$ [cm d^{-1}]
- `knc`: ndarray, shape (n,)
non-capillary hydraulic conductivity $K_{nc}(h)$ [cm d^{-1}]
- `kv`: ndarray, shape (n,)
isothermal vapor conductivity $K_v(h)$ [cm d^{-1}] if `lvap == True`
- `kt`: ndarray, shape (n,)
total hydraulic conductivity $K(h)$ [cm d^{-1}], i.e.the sum of the components
- `diff`: ndarray, shape (n,)
soil water diffusivity $D(h) = \frac{K(h)}{c(h)}$ [$\text{cm}^2 \text{d}^{-1}$], if `ldiff == True`

Table 1: Order of model parameters in the parameter vector p occurring in the interfaces to the PYTHON functions implementing the PDI model family. The parameter τ_s is the saturated tortuosity if `optknc` equals 'taus'. If `optknc` equals "ksc", the parameter τ_s in the table is the saturated capillary conductivity. Parameter c is a scaling factor for the noncapillary (film) conductivity. If `optknc` equals "ksnc", the parameter is the saturated noncapillary hydraulic conductivity, K_{snc} . The parameter h_{clip} can be set to zero or a negative value to switch off the maximum pore size constraint described in section 3.3.2 in Peters et al. (2024).

Model	Basic saturation function	Python Function	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13
PDI-VG	van Genuchten	pdi_vg	θ_r	θ_s	α	n	h_0	τ_s	τ	h_{clip}	a_{film}	c			
PDI-KOS	Kosugi	pdi_kos	θ_r	θ_s	h_m	σ_{kos}	h_0	τ_s	τ	h_{clip}	a_{film}	c			
PDI-FX	Fredlund-Xing	pdi_fx	θ_r	θ_s	α	n	m	h_0	τ_s	τ	h_{clip}	a_{film}	c		
PDI-VG-MN	van Genuchten, independent m	pdi_vg_mn	θ_r	θ_s	α	n	m	h_0	τ_s	τ	h_{clip}	a_{film}	c		
PDI-VG-BI	van Genuchten bimodal	pdi_vg_bi	θ_r	θ_s	α_1	n_1	w_2	α_2	n_2	h_0	τ_s	τ	h_{clip}	a_{film}	c
PDI-KOS-BI	Kosugi bimodal	pdi_kos_bi	θ_r	θ_s	h_{m1}	σ_{kos1}	w_2	h_{m2}	σ_{kos2}	h_0	τ_s	τ	h_{clip}	a_{film}	c

Table 2: List of python scripts which illustrate how to call some PDI functions.

Script	Content
run_pdi_vg	Defines the required input parameters, calls the pdi_vg function which calculates and returns the soil hydraulic functions, and plots the functions.
run_pdi_vg_sens_kc	Defines the required input parameters and calls the pdi_vg function twice. In the first call, the capillary hydraulic conductivity function is predicted from the water retention curve. In this case, parameter 'taus' is passed to the function. In the second run, the saturated hydraulic conductivity is passed to the function.
run_pdi_fx_vgmn	Defines the required input parameters, calls the pdi_fx function which calculates and returns the soil hydraulic functions, and plots the functions. A second call to the function pdi_vg_mn is made with the same parameter values and the results of this model are plotted in the same figure
run_pdi_kos_sens_hclip	Defines the required input parameters, calls the pdi_kos function three times, the parameter 'hclip' is varied, the hydraulic functions are plotted.
run_pdi_vg_and_export	Defines the required input parameters, calls the pdi_vg function, plots the soil hydraulic functions, and exports a file 'mater.in' which can be used for simulations with Hydrus.

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